

Evaluation of Financial Activity Results of Enterprises of Samarkand Region

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Abstract:

In this article, the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the financial situation of the enterprises operating in Samarkand region are analyzed, and the trend of changes in the creditor and receivables indicators of the enterprises is shown.

Keywords: financial - economic crisis, economically insolvent enterprises, anti-crisis management, commerce organization, damaged businesses, bankruptcy.

Introduction (Introduction)

Today, the financial and economic crisis of enterprises has prompted many countries to implement measures to initially mitigate the negative impact of the crisis and then to end it step by step. Due to this, a program of measures and methods have been developed aimed at studying the possibility of financial and economic crises in foreign countries and ensuring stable development of enterprises in the future.

Despite the measures taken, in 2022, 1.3% (55.7 thousand) of active enterprises in France, 0.4% (or 20.7 thousand) in Germany, 0.2% (12.3 thousand) in Italy, 0.2% (8.4 thousand) went bankrupt in China, 7.7% (13.5 thousand) went bankrupt in the Russian Federation¹. The fastest increase in the number of bankrupt enterprises was recorded in Bulgaria (114.3%), Slovenia (32.4%), Greece (27.3%) and the Czech Republic (21.5%).². Such cases are related to taking into account specific features of national legislation and various risk reduction methods for economic recovery of bankrupt enterprises.

¹Bankruptcy statistics. (Electronic resource):[https://vavilon.ru/statistika-bankrotstva/\(data processing 11.12.2022\)](https://vavilon.ru/statistika-bankrotstva/(data%20processing%2011.12.2022)).

²Bankruptcy statistics. (Electronic resource):[https://vavilon.ru/statistika-bankrotstva/\(data processing 11.12.2022\)](https://vavilon.ru/statistika-bankrotstva/(data%20processing%2011.12.2022)).

Over the past years, mechanisms for monitoring the signs of bankruptcy of economically insolvent enterprises, financial consolidation, pre-trial sanctions and bankruptcy implementation have been created and implemented in Uzbekistan. Nevertheless, in the conditions of market competition, there are low-efficiency and economically inefficient enterprises, and the possibility of their encountering a financial-economic crisis remains.

In this context, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev has noted: "We adopted the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" in order to continue systematic reforms and build a strong and prosperous state. This important document contains 100 specific tasks for achieving sustainable economic growth, reforming social protection, health and education systems, and ensuring the rule of law. By 2030, we have set a goal to double the income of the population and join the ranks of countries above the average according to this indicator. He noted that the poverty rate in our country has halved since 2017, and it is planned to reduce it to 7% by 2030, thanks to the policy aimed at raising the standard of living of the people."³

On the basis of scientific and methodical experiences gathered abroad and in our country, early diagnosis of enterprise crisis, substantiation of anti-crisis management strategy and development of its implementation method are very relevant and necessary research directions in the transition to the path of innovative development of the economy. and shows the relevance of the topic today.

Brief analysis of scientific works of other scientists on the topic

A general idea of the content of the process of anti-crisis management of the enterprise is given in the work of I.A. Blank, which shows the following main stages of this management: (1) continuous monitoring of the financial situation of the enterprise in order to detect early signs of a financial crisis; (2) development of a system of measures to prevent a financial crisis during the diagnosis of the enterprise's pre-crisis financial situation; (3) identification (unification) of the parameters of the financial crisis when diagnosing the beginning of the crisis; (4) study the factors leading to the crisis; (5) assessment of the company's ability to overcome the crisis; (6) choosing the directions (methods, mechanisms) of the stabilization of the enterprise corresponding to the scale of the crisis situation of the enterprise; (7) development and implementation of a comprehensive program for the recovery of the enterprise from the financial crisis; (8) control the implementation of the program for the recovery of the enterprise from the financial crisis; (9) development and implementation of measures to eliminate the negative consequences of the crisis by the enterprise.

It should be noted that each author tries to reveal one or another aspect of the term in question depending on the task put forward in his work. At the same time, the group of authors, consisting of I.K. Larionov, N.I. Bragin, A.T. Aliyev, among others, has more fully revealed the concept of anti-crisis management. They consider crisis management in two ways. In a broad sense, anti-crisis management is a systematic management of an economic object at one or another level of the economy from the point of view of resistance to the crisis. In a narrow sense, anti-crisis management is a system of organizational and management measures applied to an individual enterprise in a state of crisis, which is usually manifested in the loss of solvency. In cases where the bankruptcy is permanent and irremediable, it is terminated through the bankruptcy procedure. For crisis management in the narrow sense, it is important to determine the fact of financial insolvency of the enterprise, in which the official determination of financial insolvency is regulated by law.

The best definition of anti-crisis management was given by V. Patterson: anti-crisis management is a program of actions that should be used immediately when a negative situation occurs. Ya. Mitroff

³Uzbekistan and the UN: Steps to fight global problems together, New Uzbekistan socio-political newspaper No. 199 (988), September 29, 2023, <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/6679>

defines crisis management as a consistent interrelated assessment of various crises and forces that may threaten the company.

According to I. Kislikhina, these types are called crisis forecasting, prevention and elimination. These types of crisis management are known as warning (preventive) and reactive (responding to external influences) types. Analyzing the reactive type of crisis management is a narrow approach to understanding this situation, but it is the most common approach. For example, managing an organization against a crisis means managing it during financial insolvency (bankruptcy).

Research Methodology (Research Methodology)

In the course of the research, the dynamic approach and grouping methods were used to change the trend of the financial results of the activities of enterprises and organizations and the indicators of creditor-receivable debts..

The purpose of the article.It consists of analyzing the financial situation of the enterprises and organizations operating in Samarkand region, the important factors affecting their activities and the level of skills necessary to get the enterprises out of the crisis.

Analysis and results.

The priority tasks for socio-economic development of Samarkand region include production modernization, technical and technological re-equipment, activation of investment processes, expansion of export potential. In this case, the tasks considered important for the economy are mainly individual branches of industry and industryenterpriseswill be solved by rapidly developing the activities of the region, which will increase the industrial potential of the region.

Industryenterprisesstable operation depends largely on economic conditions in the country andenterpriseof activitydetermined by efficiency. However, increasing competition and localenterprisesthe tightening of business conditions in both domestic and foreign markets imposes special requirements on them. Effective business organization is sufficientin conditions of advanced competitionto maintain its activityand can develop. The final financial result of the activity is hisThe main measure of effectivenessindicatoris considered

Samarkand regionof enterprises *financial*The results show that their profits have increased over the past five years. For example, according to the results of 2023, all of the regionenterprises and organizations334,400.9 mln. profit was received in the amount of soums, which is 2.1 times compared to 2020 and 144779.6 million compared to 2022. is more than soum (Table 1).

Table 1 Samarkand regionenterprisesandactivities of organizationsdynamics of financial results⁴

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2023 compared to 2020, +,-
Enterprisesandof organizations financialresults (profit), mln. soum	158848.2	170120.5	189621.3	334400.9	2175552.7
Republicenterprisesandorgani zations financialRegion's share in the results (profit), %	1.2	1.4	1.3	1.7	-
Damagedenterprisesnumber,	2	2	4	9	-7

⁴Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was calculated on the basis of statistical indicators of the Statistics Department of the Samarkand region

pcs					
A damaged republicenterprisesshare of the region in the number, %	1.3	1.4	3.1	3.3	-
Republicenterprisesanddamages suffered by organizations stotal, million soum	-3277.2	1720.5	20305.0	11801.8	15079.0
Republicenterprisesanddamages suffered by organizations sshare of the region in the total, %	0.5	0.5	1.1	1.2	-
Average lloss to the enterprise stotal, million soum	-1638.6	-860.3	-5076.3	-437.1	1201.5

As part of this work next indicators to be analyzed – of enterprises and organizations *financial* results and damage number of businesses and damage quantity.

Profit is a loss before profit tax is paid enterprises (organizations) all is the final financial result determined on the basis of accounting of economic operations, which is the gross profit (loss) from the sale of products (goods, works and services), other income from the main activity, *financial* period costs of operating income and extraordinary profits, *financial* represents the amount reduced by the sum of operating expenses and extraordinary losses.

During 2020-2023, Samarkand region was damaged enterprises the number is not very large (from 2 to 9). According to the results of 2023, our republic of the region is like this enterprises its share in the number was 3.3 percent (Table 1).

Operating at a loss during the analyzed period enterprises the amount of losses from the activity has a tendency to decrease. But this trend can be seen to change by 2020. According to the end of 2020, this amount is (-) 11801.8 mln. organized soum. This is almost 2.6 times more than in 2017. Our republic of the province enterprises it can be seen that its share in the total amount of losses from its activities was in the range of 0.5 to 1.2 percent during the analyzed period (2017-2020).

It should be noted that over the years, Samarkand region has been operating at a loss the same number of enterprises is being observed, that is, in 2020 their number 2, this figure will be 9 in 2023.

However, it is running at a loss number of enterprises has little effect on the amount of damages. For example, according to the results of 2020 enterprises number was 2, and the amount of damages was (+) 3277.2 mln. organized soum. According to the results of 2021, it is working at a loss number of enterprises There are 2, and the amount of damages is (-) 1720.5 mln. organized soum. As we can see, it is working at a loss although the number of enterprises is the same the amount of losses is more than in 2021. In 2022, there are 4 working in Samarkand region businesses and organizations were identified, and their share accounted for the largest amount of losses of all analyzed years (-) 20305.0 mln. soum). These indicators will be 9 and (-) 11801.8 million in 2023, respectively. equal to soum.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the average is one which can be seen from the activity of the enterprises the average amount of damages was calculated. This amount changed every year and was 1638.6 mln. soums (2020), 860.3 mln. soums (2021), 5076.3 mln. soums (2022), and 437.1 mln. was equal to soum (2023). In the region, during 2017-2020, enterprises and organizations suffered a loss of 8.0 billion soums.

Samarkand region enterprises activity of *financial* within the analysis of the results enterprises from the activity revenues, in particular, net proceeds from the sale of products (goods, works and services); cost of sold products (goods, works and services); gross profit from the sale of products (goods, works and services), (-) loss; certain period expenses; other income from the main activity; income from financial activities; expenses on financial activities; extraordinary profits and losses; Let's look at things like net profit.

The first indicator - net revenue from the sale of products (goods, works and services) - value added tax, excise tax, gasoline for vehicles, diesel fuel, which is taken into account in the price of goods (works and services) The amount of funds received (to be received) from the sale of products (goods, works and services) without adding taxes for the consumption of heat and gas.

The information presented in Table 2 shows that by the end of 2023, Samarkand region of enterprises net income from the sale of products (goods, works and services) is 6249.2 billion. amounted to soums, which is 1.7 times more than in 2020 and 11.1% more than in 2022.

Table 2 Dynamics of financial indicators of enterprises of Samarkand region⁵

billion soum

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2023 vs. 2020, %
Net income from the sale of products (goods, works and services).	3665.4	4738.7	5622.7	6249.2	1.7 times
Cost of goods sold (goods, works and services).	2566.1	2792.3	2835.1	3027.4	118
Gross profit (loss) from the sale of products (goods, works and services)	580.5	640.4	650.5	750.1	129.2
Period costs	482.1	530.8	620.6	695.1	144.2
Other income from the main activity	65.7	73.7	79.8	88.6	134.8
<i>Financial</i> operating income	87.9	59.1	62.3	69.2	78.3
<i>Financial</i> operating expenses	63.5	85.6	77.6	78.3	123.3
Contingent profit (loss)	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.7	140
Net profit	110.5	123.6	145.3	162.7	147.2

The next indicator that we analyze is the cost of goods sold (goods, works and services) (SMT), which is the cost of production, services, material resources used in the performance of work, fixed assets, labor resources and products. implies the assessment of the value of other types of costs necessary for the implementation of the process of production, service provision, work performance. Like the first indicator, SMT in 2023 increased by 18.0% compared to 2020 and reached 3027.4 billion. amounted to soum (Table 2).

Gross profit (loss) from the sale of products (goods, works and services) is defined as the difference between the net income from the sale of products (goods, works and services) and the cost of the sold products (goods, works and services). As we can see from the data of Table 2, during the analyzed period (2020-2023) it reflected only the gross net profit, that is, no loss was seen. According to the results of 2023, this indicator will be 750.1 billion. amounted to soums, which is 29.2% more than in 2020, or 15.3% more than in 2021.

Another indicator that should be analyzed within the framework of this work is the period expenses (DX), which includes the expenses of the reporting period, sales expenses, administrative expenses

⁵Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, calculated based on the data of the Statistics Department of the Samarkand region

and other operating expenses that will be excluded from the taxable base in the future. includes According to the results of 2023, compared to 2020, the expenses of the period will be 213 billion. increased by 695.1 billion soums. amounted to soums, this indicator is 12.0% more than in 2022 (Table 2).

Financial operating expenses (MFX) – banks and other finance and creditor organizations interest on loans (banks and other financial loans organization except for interest on loans received for investments, which are included in capital investments during the investment period), including interest on overdue and extended loans, as well as exchange rate differences on foreign currency transactions and other expenses and losses on financial activities. As we can see from the data of Table 2.2, Samarkand region during the entire analyzed period of enterprises expenses on financial activities did not have certain stable growth rates. In 2021, this indicator will have the highest values compared to other years, amounting to 85.6 billion. it shows that it is soum. However, according to the results of 2023, income from financial activities will be 7.3 billion. decreased to soum. In general, in 2023, compared to 2020, this indicator increased by 23.3 percent.

The next indicator - income from financial activity includes dividends, interest, exchange rate difference, income from financial lease and other income from financial activity. The data of Table 2 shows that in 2020 this indicator has the highest values compared to other years and is 87.9 billion. it shows that it is soum. However, according to the results of 2023, income from financial activities will be 18.7 billion. decreased to soum. In general, in 2023, compared to 2020, this indicator decreased by 21.3 percent.

Extraordinary profits (losses) represent the results of extraordinary events. This indicator had positive values in 2020-2023, that is, the profit was 0.5 billion. 0.7 billion soums. organized a bag.

We will analyze another indicator - region of enterprises net profit. This is the economic operator after paying the profit tax of the reporting period which remains at the discretion of the subject final financial result. Table 2 shows that the net profit in 2023 will increase by 47.2% compared to 2020 and reach 162.7 billion. organized soum.

Samarkand region general of enterprises indicators 2015-2023 data before moving to the analysis, all debts of enterprises in general and them receivables and payables in terms of debts we will see. Province the operation of enterprises according to the results in 2023 in the amount of 4382.3 billion soums general indebtedness is allowed. Compared to 2015 debts 1854.3 billion per soum or 1.7 times increased. In the total volume of debts of enterprises creditor debts receivables debt has a larger share than (Table 3).

Table 3 Samarkand region of enterprises the trend of changes in credit and receivable indicators (billion soum)⁶

Indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Debts, total	2528.0	2668.7	2312.7	4995.6	6357.1	2579.1	5193.3	6340.1	4382.3
including:									
Accounts receivable	1171.7	1142.1	1962.0	2269.3	2787.2	1814.7	2179.2	2449.6	1448.0
Indicator share, %	46.3	42.8	45.9	45.4	43.8	70.4	42.0	38.6	33.0
Accounts payable	1356.3	1526.6	2308.4	2726.3	3569.9	764.4	3014.1	3890.5	2934.3

⁶Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, calculated based on the data of the Statistics Department of the Samarkand region.

Indicator share, %	53.7	57.2	54.1	54.6	56.2	29.6	58.0	61.4	66.9
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Debt debts long-term receivables debts, debts of buyers and customers, branch and subsidiary companies, credits to employees, credits to suppliers and contractors, budget payments and tax credits, government trust funds and insurance credits, founders' charter payments on capital investments debts, employees of on other transactions debts, other receivables debts includes. Samarkand region in 2023 enterprises and receivables of organizations debts 1448.0 billion amounted to soums, which is 2.1 times more than in 2015 (Table 3). Debt of debt total share in debts In 2023, it was 33.0 percent.

Lending in 2023 of debt total share in debts Compared to 2015, (+) increased by 13.2 percentage points and equaled 66.9%.

Based on foreign practice, it is possible to highlight common reasons for the development of insolvency process for almost all organizations. Some of the reasons are national in enterprises almost the same as developing causes. This is:

firstly, errors in the legal provision of market reforms (organization of privatization, tax system, customs policy, etc.);

and secondly, a decrease in income (in real terms) as liabilities increase. The decrease in real income is due to the decrease in the population's solvency, the increase in prices, and the accumulation of surplus goods in the market due to the sharp increase in the volume of imports of better quality goods. The reason for the increase in obligations is the presence of excess reserves in organizations, they by implementation of ineffective long-term financial investments;

thirdly, severe competitive conditions (mainly the absence of competitive advantages and unwillingness to work in this environment);

fourth, unreasonable and disproportionate expansion of the organization's economic activity;

fifth, lack of effective corporate controls;

sixth, management's inability to implement strategic, tactical and operational management in accordance with the market conditions of business operations (low skill level, lack of experience, reluctance to use new management methods, etc.);

The experience of Western firms shows that insolvency alone, losses and even errors in the legal provision of market reforms, declining revenues when liabilities are already increasing, and intense competitive conditions do not mean that bankruptcy is inevitable. However, they more or less create the possibility of bankruptcy. A foreigner in this sense specialists 38% of the bankrupt firms studied were operating at a loss enterprises, and the remaining 62 percent are profitable enterprises organized. About 50 percent of profitable businesses that fail are low-profit and financially unstable businesses, with low profitability production volume is unreasonable increased in a way enterprises and had satisfactory profitability and financial stability indicators, but carried out a marketing policy based on risk established enterprises.

Belonging to the above groups enterprises The direct reasons for the bankruptcy were different. Damage is running and low profitable enterprises have gone bankrupt due to a minor additional failure in the market (eg, client bankruptcy, late payment, etc.). Profitable firms fail due to a strict marketing policy that does not take into account the market conditions, or due to serious losses in the implementation of individual investment projects, or for reasons unrelated to the firm's activities (bankruptcy of a major client, significant changes and b.) were subject to bankruptcy. Considering this, our republic is not only economically weak, operating at a loss and low profitable financial

situation of enterprises indicators, but in such situations the survivor or it is appropriate to analyze the economic, financial and management activities of bankrupt enterprises.

Summary

The analysis of the socio-economic development of Samarkand region, the concentration of its economic and production potential, and the research of the anti-crisis measures applied to the enterprises made it possible to draw the following conclusions.

Today, the creation of a solid basis for the further development of industries and sectors, as well as the regions of our country, is being ensured in our republic. The positive dynamics of socio-economic development of Samarkand region in 2020-2023 is also observed in other indicators.

As a result of the implementation of complex programs to increase the competitiveness of the economy, the gross regional product of Samarkand region in 2023 increased by 5.9 times compared to 2020 in real prices.

In Samarkand region, during 2020-2023, the volume of investments in fixed capital increased 6 times. In this period, such growth was ensured mainly due to the implementation of active investment policy aimed at modernization of economic sectors, technical and technological renewal, acceleration of implementation of strategic investment projects and construction of new production facilities.

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